

Archiving Multiplatform Conspiracy Social Spaces: A Case Study of the QAnon Counter-Public

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Recent political events, including the COVID-19 pandemic, the invasion of Ukraine, as well as the 2020 and 2024 American elections, have underscored the growing prevalence of conspiracy narratives in public discourse (Enders et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2021; Ellison, 2024). Although such narratives are far from unprecedented (Barkun, 2003; Butter, 2020), their contemporary ubiquity is closely tied to QAnon's emergence on social networking sites (SNS). In this study, we argue that QAnon functions as a mobilizing phenomenon, fostering transmedia conspiracy content within a dispersed network of social spaces. Its foundation lies in an asymmetrical relationship between Q—an enigmatic figure who posted cryptic “drops” from 2017 to 2022 on platforms such as 4chan, 8chan, and 8kun (Zuckerman, 2019; Rothschild, 2020)—and the Anons, a decentralized group tasked with interpreting and disseminating these drops. Q's narratives revolve around a covert battle between allegedly corrupt Democratic elites in a “deep state” and patriotic forces led by Donald Trump, challenging American institutions, media, and electoral processes (Papasavva et al., 2021). While many of these narratives initially emerged in fringe online communities, they were rapidly amplified into mainstream arenas such as Reddit, YouTube, Facebook, and Twitter (O'Connor et al., 2020; Bloom and Moskalenko, 2020; Miller, 2021; Hannah, 2021; Engel, 2022). This amplification culminated in the “normification” (De Zeeuw et al., 2020) of QAnon's ideas, whereby fringe content infiltrated broader public discourse and became part of mainstream debates.

In this respect, Q and the Anons align with Fraser's (1990) notion of a counter-public—“parallel discursive arenas” in which marginalized groups “develop alternative interpretations of their identities, interests, and needs” (p. 81). Yet QAnon's digital orientation modernizes this concept, reflecting what Jackson and Foucault Welles (2015) describe as a “networked counter-public.” This conspiratorial network crystallizes through deliberate, though seemingly organic, efforts to integrate fringe narratives into mainstream discourse (Dilley et al., 2022; Rossetti & Zaman, 2023). Additionally, the fragmentation of authority in digital contexts has enabled ad hoc elites to establish communities beyond traditional power structures in media and politics.

Despite extensive research on QAnon's anglophone origins, significant gaps endure. First, QAnon's counter-public has shifted to alt-tech social spaces—Telegram, Odysee, and Truth Social—after its bans on mainstream platforms. These environments, often characterized by minimal moderation, decentralized hosting, and a tolerance for controversial or extremist content under “free speech” principles (Dowling, 2023; Siapera, 2023), remain underexplored, complicating any large-scale or systematic analysis of their content. Second, although QAnon's transnational presence has been documented (Labbe et al., 2020; Hoseini et al., 2021; Paschetto et al., 2022; Murru, 2022; Zehring & Domahidi, 2023), the adaptation of these narratives for French-, Italian-, and German-speaking audiences is poorly understood. We know little about the sociocultural processes that enable local adaptations or about the key figures who extend QAnon's ideological reach across linguistic and national boundaries.

This study addresses these gaps by examining the transmedia content produced by central actors within QAnon's networked counter-public across alternative platforms. Emphasizing data extraction, analysis, and archiving, we investigate how device-driven content, research practices, and platform infrastructures converge to construct, circulate, and preserve QAnon narratives in a mutable digital ecosystem. Employing a “mixed-method approach” (Crossley & Edwards, 2016; Snelson, 2016; Aguilera & Chevalier, 2021) that integrates computational tools with digital ethnography, our

methodology reveals the social and cultural practices that shape QAnon’s networked counter-public. This framework aligns with the “computational turn” (Hase et al., 2023), wherein researchers devise ways to systematically capture and analyze transmedia productions on SNS.

Earlier work centered on accessible Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter to map interactions, identify influential actors, and visualize information flows (Kosinski et al., 2015 ;Firdaniza et al., 2021; Antonakaki et al., 2021; Coromina & Padilla, 2022). Despite stricter limitations introduced after the Cambridge Analytica Scandal, API availability facilitated the development of replicable tools for examining socio-technical structures and negative behaviors such as bots, echo chambers, and disinformation (Marres & Gerlitz, 2015; Colleoni et al., 2014; Bessi & Ferrara, 2016; Airoldi et al., 2016; Gray et al., 2020). However, alt-tech platforms like Telegram, Odysee and Truth Social lack robust documentation for API usage, prompting us to devise adaptive strategies for data collection. We created custom codes to enable an efficient snowball sampling process (Chan, 2019; Buehling & Heft, 2023), starting with a small set of initial channels that expanded as shared material was traced to newly discovered channels. Ultimately, this yielded millions of messages and shared content (see annex 1).

We then analyzed the resulting dataset using graphical representations (e.g., monthly posting by language) and Social Network Analysis (SNA) with Gephi (Bastian et al., 2009), which highlights influential nodes, clusters, and interaction patterns in conspiracy networks (Logan et al., 2023). Yet SNA alone offers only a macro-level viewpoint, leaving the sociocultural nuances of central conspiracy actors unexamined. To address this, we conducted an in-depth study of Les DéQodeurs—three prominent figures in the francophone conspiracy community, who operated multiple accounts on platforms lacking APIs. Data collection combined crawling to locate interlinked web pages (Kausar et al., 2013) with static scraping of simple HTML sites and dynamic scraping, which simulates user actions to uncover hidden content on platforms without official APIs (Lotfi et al., 2021)—including Rumble, CrowdBunker, and X (see annex 2). This approach allowed us to build a transplatform posting graph, revealing cross-platform strategies and activity patterns underpinning QAnon’s counter-public.

Subsequent qualitative observations of high-profile channels and accounts drew on digital ethnography (Kozinets, 1997; Jeanne-Perrier, 2010; Jouët & Le Caroff, 2013; Caliandro, 2018), illuminating the social, cultural, and discursive foundations of conspiracy networks. We also invoked the concept of digital affordances, derived from Gibson’s (1979) original ecological approach to perception and Norman’s (1988) emphasis on perceived affordances in design. As updated by Ronzhyn et al. (2022), digital affordances in social media research refer to “the perceived, actual, or imagined properties of social media that emerge through the interplay of technological, social, and contextual factors.” This theoretical lineage clarifies how both conspiracy influencers and researchers adapt platform usage to their distinct objectives and constraints, illustrating the reciprocal relationship between user behaviors and platform features.

Our first key finding introduces “conspiracy influencers,” central figures who leverage Q’s drops to gain social and economic capital. Operating across transnational conspiracy communities located linguistically (see annex 3), these individuals fall into three categories: Interfacers, Transmedia influencers, and Unimedia influencers. Interfacers imitate Q’s persona, bridging global QAnon content with localized communities; Transmedia influencers combine video productions, articles, and livestreams to interpret current events; and Unimedia influencers concentrate on a single content format, forging deep ties with audiences while maintaining influence in broader ecosystems. Despite varied strategies, all prioritize visibility—expanding reach—and persistence—ensuring content remains accessible over time (Boyd, 2010). By constructing complex infrastructures of follower networks, accounts, and targeted content, they cater to audience preferences, circumvent moderation, and reinforce QAnon’s message.

Platform choice deeply shapes these practices. Odysee is often employed as a video repository that allows limited interactivity, while Telegram and Truth Social foster audience engagement and reciprocal content exchange. Yet each platform’s affordances also hinge on user perceptions. For instance, European conspiracy communities have made minimal inroads into Truth Social, which remains largely American in user base, implying that visibility aligns with entrenched audience habits. The prominence of English-speaking influencers underscores how adopting an anglophone-driven

approach bolsters broader impact, even though a considerable volume of Telegram content is produced in German.

Among francophone multimedia influencers, Les DéCodeurs demonstrates how platform affordances guide content production. Active on eleven platforms, they strive to maximize visibility by aligning their narratives with national and global events (see annex 4). They recontextualize material from French and global media alongside Q's drops, presenting and debating excerpts live, thereby weaving a continuous transmedia narrative. Technical refinements, such as green screens and polished visual design, lend a veneer of professionalism, while lively Telegram-based discussions nurture parasocial bonds. They also archive videos on Odysee to preserve content, guarding against "deplatforming." Ultimately, Les DéCodeurs illustrates how content production practices respond to audience demands for easy, up-to-date materials, simultaneously exporting conspiracy agendas across national boundaries.

A second key finding shows that these influencers' practices align with what Weltevrede (2016) terms "research affordances." The same visibility and persistence valued by influencers also prove pivotal for scholarship: archived material supports in-depth analysis of how conspiracy narratives evolve, tracks cross-linguistic adaptations, and elucidates sociotechnical factors influencing their spread. By storing content across multiple repositories, conspiracy influencers inadvertently build structured data that researchers can use to document shifting discourse over time. This mirrors a "follow the natives" approach (Caliandro, 2018), integrating user-driven behaviors into technical inquiry. However, platforms perpetually evolve through API updates, policy changes, and new Terms of Service (ToS)—thus research affordances remain inherently unstable. As Marres and Gerlitz (2015) suggest, refining existing methods, rather than designing entirely new ones, may be most effective, acknowledging the triangular interplay among research objectives, mediums, and methods. Indeed, some alt-tech platforms that offer "secluded" spaces for extremist communities can also provide ample data-collection opportunities, as illustrated by our extensive datasets.

Nonetheless, navigating these research affordances brings obstacles. Telegram's large-group calls, for example, remain inaccessible, while new Truth Social firewalls have rendered certain datasets unreplicable. Although Telegram and Odysee appear less restrictive than mainstream SNS, they still present legal and ethical dilemmas. Odysee's ToS explicitly prohibit unauthorized scraping, despite its public-facing content. Researchers must also address privacy obligations, especially with massive multimedia datasets (Fiesler et al., 2016). Although cloud-based solutions (i.e., Google Drive and Google Collab) can mitigate storage and data processing issues, they introduce additional costs and data stewardship concerns.

Ethical considerations arise when disseminating findings as well. Our Odysee and Telegram datasets can be hosted, for instance on Humanum, yet legal constraints deter public release of parallel datasets from Truth Social. These restrictions underscore the need for interdisciplinary cooperation among legal, technical, and social-science specialists to refine data-collection tactics and comply with ever-shifting regulations. Some scholars advocate a "data activist" stance (Venturini & Rogers, 2019; Caliandro, 2021), maintaining that platforms integral to public dialogue must not lock down data without accountability. Bruns (2019) similarly highlights the ethical and legal imperative for independent research, asserting that platforms profiting from user data have a responsibility to facilitate analyses of their societal influence. Still, occupying these activist or pioneering positions can be fraught with risks if platforms impose legal hurdles. Researchers must therefore navigate a delicate balance between seeking robust, large-scale data and preserving ethical and legal standards in the realm of alternative digital environments.

Annexes

Annex 1. Overview of Collected Corpora by Platform and Depth				
Platform	Depth	Channels	Content	Shared Content
Telegram	Depth 0	15	1,075,351	408,835
	Depth 1	5,709	93,428,687	31,149,497
	Depth 2	134,221	532,430,305	467,242,455
Odysee	Depth 0	80	38,906	3,083
	Depth 1	328	301,721	37,169
	Depth 2	1,748	1,273,486	229,479
	Depth 3	9,498	3,873,357	466,872
	Depth 4	13,432	4,962,595	516,803
Truth Social	Depth 0	8	4,630	3,336
	Depth 1	410	5,050,880	2,896,326
	Depth 2	61,427	239,234,822	177,184,754

Annex 2. Overview of Collected Corpora Related to Les Décodeurs	
Websites	3,036
Telegram	7,125
Odysee	483
Rumble	307
VK	13
Crowd Bunker	74
X	1,958

Annex 3: Graphical Renderings of Conspiracy Communities with Gephi

From left to right: Telegram, Odyssee, and Truth Social. Each Gephi-generated graph displays the distinct communities identified using the Louvain method, with the most influential actors labeled within each cluster.

Annex 4: Graphical Rendering of Monthly Publications by Les DéQodeurs

This visualization depicts how Les DéQodeurs distribute their content over time across various social media platforms, illustrating the cadence and reach of their posting activity.

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